

Communication and Dissemination Plan

D13.1

Authors:

Distribution Level	PU
Responsible Partner	Daniela Bernardo (EUI)
Checked by WP leader [name surname]	Date: 26.02.2021 Daniela Bernardo (EUI)
Verified by the appointed Reviewers [name surname, name surname]	Date: 26.02.2021 Antonello Monti (FhG) Stephan Groß (FhG)
Approved by Project Coordinator	Date: 26.02.2021 Antonello Monti (FhG)

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About OneNet

OneNet will provide a seamless integration of all the actors in the electricity network across Europe to create the conditions for a synergistic operation that optimizes the overall energy system while creating an open and fair market structure.

The project OneNet (One Network for Europe) is funded through the EU's eighth Framework Programme Horizon 2020. It is titled "TSO – DSO Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" and responds to the call "Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future (LC)".

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to adapt to this changing environment and adjust their current business model to accommodate faster reactions and adaptive flexibility. This is an unprecedented challenge requiring an unprecedented solution. For this reason, the two major associations of grid operators in Europe, ENTSO-E and EDSO, have activated their members to put together a unique consortium.

OneNet will see the participation of a consortium of over 70 partners. Key partners in the consortium include: already mentioned ENTSO-E and EDSO, Elering, EDP Distribution, RWTH Aachen University, University of Comillas, VITO, European Dynamics, Ubitech, Engineering, and the EU's Florence School of Regulation (Energy).

The key elements of the project are:

1. Definition of a common market design for Europe: this means standardized products and key parameters for grid services which aim at the coordination of all actors, from grid operators to customers;
2. Definition of a Common IT Architecture and Common IT Interfaces: this means not trying to create a single IT platform for all the products but enabling an open architecture of interactions among several platforms so that anybody can join any market across Europe; and
3. Large-scale demonstrators to implement and showcase the scalable solutions developed throughout the project. These demonstrators are organized in four clusters coming to include countries in every region of Europe and testing innovative use cases never validated before.

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1 Introduction

The scope of the dissemination campaign is three-fold:

- developing a Communication and Dissemination Plan will help raise awareness on the project and possibly create synergies and new levels of cooperation among the players, customers and stakeholders for “One Network for Europe”;
- Dissemination activities (along with the interactive forum “GRIFOn) will create consensus and acceptance of the established solution externally and internally; and
- The solution has commercial value in the grid services market. In this respect, communication activities will help ensure products are more marketable.

The main communication tasks each take a different approach in order to complement each other. Task 13.1 is the foundation to develop the project’s communication activities, composed by the main elements that are key for the project identity: corporate identity, documents templates, brochure and website. The project website will provide clear and engaging information about the project activities and events and will gather all of the project’s publications. The website will be constantly updated and will benefit from a strong connection with the social media channels as well as hosting a project blog, which will feature valuable insights from the sector, including contributions from the partners.

Task 13.2 covers the communication and outreach activities aimed at communicating to a more general audience. Specific actions will be: creating and managing a new dedicated database; developing a project video; creating awareness of the project through social media (LinkedIn, Twitter); producing articles, interviews and webinars to be published on the project website; preparing newsletters to be distributed to the OneNet database; and supporting project partners in contributing to the project blog.

Task 13.3, Advisory and Dissemination Board (ADB) will serve as an opportunity to identify changes in the framework, new challenges and opportunities. In addition, the ADB will advise in the communication of results to stakeholders and help opening dissemination paths in preparation for exploitation

Milestones:

- Project website (M5);
- Databases of stakeholders created (M38): Gathering relevant contacts from all the partners involved, creating and managing a new dedicated database;
- Open days at three trial sites presenting and discussing prototype solutions (M39): To promote the interests of the project, this task will assume the organisational and logistical enabling of communication activities such as workshops, innovation and dissemination events, special sessions in conferences and fairs. Open days will take place at the trial sites and will feature guided

demonstrations of the functionality of selected results. In-person events such as these will take place only when the health situation linked to the COVID-19 pandemic allows it. If appropriate and feasible, consideration of replacement online activities will be undertaken;

- Two exploitation workshops (M40): Two exploitation workshops will be organised during the development of the project to identify the options, to align partners view and to prepare the correspondent plans; and
- One final OneNet conference (M41): A final conference will gather experts in the sector to discuss the innovation proposed by OneNet.

2 Target Audience

The target audience has been identified based on a number of factors, including: analysis of audiences from previous projects implemented by the consortium, mapping of partners and stakeholders, and research of similar projects external to the consortium.

The key audience groups have been identified as follows:

- System Operators (TSOs, DSOs);
- Energy Regulators;
- Policy Makers;
- Aggregators;
- ICT, IoT providers;
- Market operators;
- Academia;
- Consumers (Industry, Prosumers and energy communities, EU Citizens);
- Power Producers; and
- Energy Suppliers.

Some of ways the project will further identify audiences and create a “user persona” include:

- Customer surveys;
- Research similar projects and topics;
- Collection of demographic data from OneNet’s website analytics; and
- Analysis of newsletter subscribers and social media followers.

3 Key communication goals and actions

We will direct our communications efforts towards the following goals:

- Promote the activities and the results of the project;
- Identify, reach, and engage with stakeholders;
- Improve fruitful synergies and internal communication between the WPs;
- Drive and support innovation in the grid services market;
- Make the produced knowledge more accessible, inclusive, and actionable;
- Facilitate interaction and feedback/input on our work;
- Improve press & media relations.*

Where possible, “OneNet” all resources will be available in open access.

**Members of the press and press officers will be mapped and periodically contacted with relevant information about the project under the form of press releases.*

4 Key messages of the project

In our external communications flow, the scope of the project translates in the key messages that will be disseminated through our channels:

- OneNet aims at removing the entry barriers to the flex market and ensuring seamless coordination between grid and market operation;
- OneNet aims to create unique synergies between all players at EU and national level; and
- OneNet is more than a project: it’s also a platform of cooperation.

5 Streams of communications

For this project, we identified three streams of communications:

1. **Internal communications, among the partners of the consortium.** The internal stream can be self-regulated, in order to allow flexibility and to take advantage of any interesting initiative coming from the members. We will select the channels and tools based on the different needs and preferences of the internal users and we will follow a bottom-up approach.
2. **External communications (led by WP13).** External communications are centralised and under the responsibility of WP13. Communications tasks, roles and goals will be communicated in advance and will be based on the communications plan developed by WP13. Input and updates from all the other work packages are key for the success of the communications activities, to this end, an excel file has been shared on the OneNet Teams account to collect input on a weekly basis (which is considered part of the internal communications).
3. **GRIFOn communications (led by WP12).** The communications of GRIFOn will be led by the WP12 (with the support of WP13 which will strengthen the links with OneNet project). Especially in the first phase of the project, the dissemination tasks of OneNet and GRIFOn complement each other and proceed in parallel. GRIFOn should capitalise on the results and audiences reached by OneNet and gain full autonomy in the future.

6 External communications channels

Communications channels are medium (both digital and analog) through which our key messages are disseminated to the audiences.

- Website: <https://onenet-project.eu/> ;
- Newsletter;
- GRIFOn;
- Social media;
 - OneNet Twitter;
 - OneNet LinkedIn;
- Public relations (i.e. press);
- Partners' websites; and
- Webinars / LIVE and Online Events.

7 Planning

The scheduling of communication activities will follow the timing of all of the project's deliverables:

- New publications;
- Milestones;
- Events;
- News from the project network;
- Consultations; and
- GRIFOn activities

The planning includes a list of monthly activities and objectives:

- 10 social media posts, blogs/ news;
- 2 multimedia content to break down and simplify messages;
- 2 visuals i.e. banners, flyers;
- 1 blog post;
- external newsletters (to be sent twice a year);
- (when due) press releases;
- monthly reports and tracking of views;
- participation at events and conferences; and
- collecting input from all partners regarding their communication activities (presentation at events, newsletter, blog articles, news, publications...).

Regular statistics on the impact of the website and social media will be gathered and analysed by the WP13 leaders, helping the project coordinator and partners revise and improve the communication strategy.

WP13 will facilitate and support the participation in main events in the field by doing preliminary research to find the best forums to disseminate the project and network; creating dedicated promo material; doing live coverage of the events on the website and social media; actively engaging with journalists and event organisers and launching partnerships to maximise the communications outreach.

8 Measuring the impact of our dissemination activities

In order to assess the performances of our communications strategy, we need to:

- Set benchmarks;
- Map, identify and analyse similar projects;
- Tailor tone and communications to the audiences;
- Get in touch with similar projects; and
- Measure growth over time and (if needed) revise the strategy.

Set benchmarks

Aspirational benchmarks (realistic amounts of followers / views / engagement that we can achieve) will be measured by:

- Looking at - and comparing- the metrics for knowledge leaders and similar projects in the field; and
- Looking at - and comparing - sectoral benchmarking on specific channels: an aggregate of data from projects, companies or institutions that operate in the same sector as OneNet on a specific channel/ social media.

Among the relevant sectors to be used as a comparison, the following will be observed: higher education, tech and software, research centres and universities, think tanks and nonprofit organisations.

Map, identify and analyse similar projects

We will collect information on all the projects / initiatives / companies that belong to our target list. Identifying and analysing similar projects will serve the purpose of leveraging data, to be able to drive relevant conclusions and - if needed - adjust our targets and strategy.

Tailor tone and communications to the audiences and get in touch with similar projects

Once we have a clear understanding of our audience and similar projects, we will be able to tailor our communications around them, by targeting them and establish contact.

Measure growth over time and (if needed) revise our strategy

We should evaluate outcomes against benchmarks and objectives, set new objective and - if needed - revise the strategy as we go. Tools to measure growth: Twitter analytics; LinkedIn analytics; Google Analytics; Contacts established.

9 Internal communications

Among the WPs, the partners and stakeholders communications will be carried through periodical meetings, emails, Teams shared documents and newsletters. The Project Management Team (PMT) meets monthly and discusses and shares important internal information. The PMT also agrees on important internal messages to be circulated, normally led by the Coordinator. Each Work Package then has its own internal emailing group and structured communication paths centered around periodic meetings that fit with the respective tasks to be completed. Teams is used by all members of the consortium to ensure efficient and swift real-time communication. The document library function of Teams is also utilised to store common important files, such as the log of communication and dissemination activities that will ultimately feed into the periodic reporting to the European Commission.

An internal newsletter will be produced every quarter of a year and shared among all partners. It will collect the dissemination activities, publications, deliverables, news, blog posts and reports from the project during the referent period.

10 OneNet Advisory and Dissemination Board

The OneNet Advisory and Dissemination Board (ADB) will assess the overall OneNet approach, use cases and field trials and their implications for the European energy system. The ADB will be asked to regularly provide concrete recommendations for the OneNet project to consider adopting in its continued implementation. ADB meetings will also serve as an opportunity to identify changes in the framework and new challenges and opportunities for the proposed OneNet solutions. In addition, the ADB will advise in the communication of results to stakeholders and help opening dissemination paths in preparation for exploitation. Members of the ADB will help communicate the project results and insights and thereby ensure European-wide acceptance and usability of the OneNet project outcomes.

OneNet aims to create an ADB with a more technical orientation. Board meetings would serve to provide feedback on specific points that are critical to the project progress at that point in time. The ADB shall therefore consist of leading representatives of the critical energy infrastructure and ICT sectors, who are not directly involved in the activities of OneNet. The OneNet consortium aims to create a Board that is composed of members with diverse backgrounds as regards technical expertise and/or business activities relevant for the project. Ideally, the Board is also diverse and balanced as regards geography and gender. In addition, OneNet will aim to create some overlaps with Advisory Boards from relevant other (previous or ongoing) H2020 projects, specifically INTERFACE and CoordiNet.